

ORGANIC REACTIONS WITH POLYPHOSPHORIC ACID. PART V,
INTRAMOLECULAR ACYLATION WITH LACTONES:
cyclopentenones FROM δ -LACTONES

BY SUKH DEV AND CHARANJIT RAI

Intramolecular acylation of lactones to yield *cyclopentenones* in the presence of polyphosphoric acid has been extended to δ -lactones. Based on this, convenient, possibly general, routes to bicyclo-[0:3:3]-octane and bicyclo-[0:3:4]-nonane systems have been described. The reaction has been discussed from the mechanistic point of view.

Various δ -lactones have been converted into the corresponding *cyclopentenones* by the P_2O_5 method (Frank and Pierle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 724; Ansell and Hey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2875), but the yields have been rather unsatisfactory. Since polyphosphoric acid (PPA) has been shown (Rai and Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1957, 35, 178) to be capable of yielding *cyclopentenones* from γ -lactones in excellent yields, the method has been extended to δ -lactones. It has been thus possible to synthesise α :3-dimethyl*cyclopenten-1-one* (I), bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^7 -octen-1-one (II) and bicyclo-[0:3:4]- Δ^8 -nonen-1-one (III) in very good yields.

The general method of synthesis consists in the preparation of a δ -oxo-carboxylic acid, preferably by a Michael addition to a β -keto-ester, followed by hydrolysis; the δ oxo-carboxylic acid is next reduced to yield a δ -lactone, which on intramolecular acylation in the presence of PPA furnishes the *cyclopentenone*. The method is capable of general extension.

δ -Oxo-carboxylic Acids.—The Michael addition of ethyl methylacetoacetate to ethyl acrylate smoothly furnished ethyl α -methyl- α -acetylglutarate (IVa) in an excellent yield; its preparation was previously reported by Wislicenus and Limpach (*Annalen*, 1878, 192, 128) who effected the condensation of ethyl methylacetoacetate with ethyl β -iodopropionate. Ketonic hydrolysis of the product afforded the required γ methyl- δ -oxo-*n*-caproic acid (IVb).

Condensation of ethyl *cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate* with ethyl β -chloro- or β -bromopropionate gave ethyl *cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2- β -propionate* (Va) (Cook and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 953); this was, however, far more conveniently obtained by the Michael addition of ethyl *cyclopentanone carboxylate* to ethyl acrylate. It was observed that when the Michael reaction was carried out in the presence of

sodium ethoxide, ring-fission occurred, affording ethyl γ -carbethoxysuberate in 90% yield; however, when the addition was catalysed by potassium *tert.*-butoxide (Sukh Dev, *Science & Culture*, 1950, 16, 31) no cleavage of the primary reaction product (Va) occurred. Hydrolysis of (Va) with dilute hydrochloric acid furnished the requisite cyclopentanone-2- β -propionic acid (Vb).

[a: R = COOEt; R' = Et]

[b: R = R' = H]

Similarly (VIa) (cf. Haworth and Mavin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1012) was readily obtained by the interaction of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and ethyl acrylate in the presence of potassium *tert.*-butoxide; hydrolysis afforded (VIb) in 85% yield.

δ -Lactones.—The δ -lactones (VII, VIII and IX) were prepared by the reduction of the corresponding δ -oxo-carboxylic acids, followed by acidification. The reduction was effected quite smoothly either by the Raney-nickel alloy-alkali method (Schwenk *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1944, 9, 175) or by the sodium borohydride method (Chaikin and Brown, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 122).

From a consideration of molecular models it appears that only *cis*-cyclopentanol-2- β -propionic acid can readily lactonise to (VIII); this would indicate the $\gamma\delta$ -cyclopentano- δ -valerolactone (VIII), prepared by the procedures described in this communication, should consist essentially of the *cis*-isomer. This conclusion appears to be supported by the fact that whereas both (VII) and (IX) could be prepared in 90% yields by the NaBH_4 method, cyclopentanone-2- β -propionic acid (Vb) affords the desired lactone (VIII) in only 50% yield.

The preparation of $\gamma\delta$ -cyclohexano- δ -valerolactone (IX) by different methods has been previously described in the literature (Nenitzescu and Przemetzky, *Ber.*, 1941, 74, 676; Frank and Pierle, *loc. cit.*; cf. Mathieson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 177). Just like the present preparation, these products should be mixtures of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers.

cyclopentenones.—The δ -lactones (VII, VIII, IX) on treatment with PPA furnished the corresponding cyclopentenones (I, II, III). It has been found that for each lactone there is an optimum set of conditions for the PPA reaction. The lowest temperature

at which the reaction proceeded with a reasonable speed, was always selected for determining the optimum time for the reaction; at higher temperatures the decomposition of the cyclopentenone became considerable.

$\gamma\delta$ -Dimethyl- δ -valerolactone (VII), when treated with PPA at 97° for 4 hours, afforded the maximum yield (80%) of 2:3-dimethyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1-one (I); the reaction was exceedingly slow at 80° . Frank *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1379) have reported its preparation from γ -methyl- γ -ethylbutyrolactone (X) by the P_2O_5 method in a very poor yield. It is clear from the extinction coefficient of their product (*vide Experimental*) that their sample of the cyclopentenone was impure.

$\gamma\delta$ -cyclopentano- δ -valerolactone (VIII) underwent intramolecular acylation smoothly even at 60° and after $4\frac{1}{2}$ hours of treatment furnished bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^7 -octen-1-one (II) in 92% yield. This compound has been synthesised recently by Cope and Schmitz (*ibid.*, 1950, 72, 3056) from 2:5-dichloro- $\Delta^{1:5}$ -cyclooctadiene (XI).

The conversion of $\gamma\delta$ -cyclohexano- δ -valerolactone (IX) to 4:5:6:7-tetrahydroindan-1-one (III) was found to be incomplete under a variety of conditions. At temperatures higher than 80° , the decomposition of the ketone was considerable. Table I records the results of a series of experiments conducted at $80^\circ \pm 2^\circ$. It is clear from these data that though the conversion to the ketone increases with the time of heating, the overall yield of (III), based on the lactone, falls due to the considerable loss of the material as a result of prolonged heating. Frank and Pierle (*loc. cit.*) carried out the conversion of the lactone (IX) to the tetrahydroindanone (III) by the P_2O_5 method, and reported a yield of 13%. Mathieson (*loc. cit.*) obtained the ketone (III) in a yield of 16% by the P_2O_5 -benzene method, and in a yield of 7.5% by the zinc chloride-acetic anhydride method from the spiro lactone (XII).

TABLE I
Intramolecular acylation of (IX).

No.	Time *	n_D^{20} .	Yield †.	Ketone content.	Absolute yield of the ketone based on the lactone.
1	1 hr.	1.5068	0.70 g.	50.43%	51.9%
2	2	1.5125	0.62	67.89	61.9
3	3	1.5150	0.62	74.33	67.8
4	4	1.5160	0.60	76.17	67.2

* Time for which the reaction was carried out at $80^\circ \pm 2^\circ$.

† Yield of the distillable material*(b.p. $130-150^\circ/13$ mm) from a PPA reaction using 0.005 M of the lactone.

It has been suggested (Johnson and Peterson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1366 ; Frank and Pierle, *loc. cit.*) that the intramolecular acylation of lactones proceeds *via* the corresponding unsaturated acid. The lacto-enolic tautomerism is now well recognised (Linstead and Rydon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 580 ; Boorman and Linstead, *ibid.*, 1935, 258 ; Johnson, Petersen and Schneider, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 74 ; Mathieson, *loc. cit.*). It appears feasible to consider that in the PPA-catalysed reactions (Sukh Dev, *this Journal*, 1957, **34**, 169) of this type the first step should be the rapid establishment of the reversible equilibrium of the lactone and P_2O_5 with the complex (A)*. This, either by a two-step process passing through (B), or by a concerted mechanism with the transition state (C), should yield the intermediate (D) after taking up the ejected proton †. The intermediate (D) then cyclises through the usual oxo-carbonium ion to provide the cyclic unsaturated ketone.

The formation of the intermediate (D) will be the first rate-determining step on which will be superimposed the rate of ionisation of (D) to give the observed rate of the conversion of the lactone to the ketone. If the formation of (D) passes through (C), the two *cis-trans*-isomers of, say, the lactone (IX), should react at different rates due to the preferred anti-geometry of the transition state ; and since from both isomers (D) will be the same, the observed rate of the reaction can be utilised to possibly distinguish between the two mechanisms. It is hoped to continue the work on these lines.

*In these formulae only a δ -lactone has been depicted ; the same will hold good for a γ -lactone.

† A possible transition state transferring the proton intramolecularly can be :

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The spectra were measured in 95% ethanolic solution on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

2:3-Dimethylcyclopenten-1-one (I)

Ethyl 2-Methyl- α -acetylglutarate (IVa).—To a solution of potassium (0.1 g.) in *tert.*-butanol (15 c.c.), contained in a 3-necked flask carrying a Hershberg stirrer, a dropping funnel, a thermometer and an outlet tube connected to a guard-tube (SiO_2 -gel), ethyl methylacetoacetate (18.0 g., 0.125 M) was added in one lot; *tert.*-BuOH (10 c.c.) was used for washing in the last traces of the keto-ester. To the above stirred mixture, ethyl acrylate (16.65 g., 0.15 M) was let in dropwise at a rate that the temperature did not go beyond 30° (when the reaction temperature touched 30°, the flask was cooled externally with tap water and the contents maintained at 25-30°); this required (*ca.*) 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature (22-25°) for 15 hours. The light orange-coloured product was acidified with glacial acetic acid (2 c.c.) and the resulting pale yellow solution diluted with benzene (50 c.c.), washed with brine (50 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was flashed off (column) and the residue fractionated to give the required product as a colorless liquid, b.p. 114-15°/0.6 mm, 132°/2 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4410, yield 27.5 g. (90%). FeCl_3 test was negative (Wislicenus and Limpach, *loc.cit.*, record b.p. 280-81°). (Found: C, 59.4; H, 7.9. Calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5$: C, 59.0; H, 8.2%).

*γ -Methyl- δ -oxo-*n*-caproic Acid* (IVb).—A mixture of the above condensation product (24.5 g.), HCl (C.P., 50 c.c.) and water (25 c.c.) was gently refluxed in an oil-bath (135-40°) for 24 hours. The aqueous HCl was then distilled off under reduced pressure (water-pump) from a steam-bath and the residue fractionated to provide: (a) fore-run, b.p. 85°-125°/1.2 mm, yield 1.5 g. and (b) the required keto-acid (IVb), b.p. 125-26°/1.2 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4460, yield 11.8 g. (82%). (Found: C, 58.2; H, 8.4. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 58.3; H, 8.3%).

$\gamma\delta$ -Dimethyl- δ -valerolactone (VII): (i) *By the Raney-nickel alloy-alkali Method.*—The keto-acid (7.2 g., 0.05 M) was dissolved in aqueous NaOH (25 g. in 150 c.c. of water) and the resulting solution was stirred and treated as such with the Ni-Al alloy (-40 mesh; 12 g.) in small portions during 2 hours; excessive foaming was avoided. The reaction mixture was next stirred and heated at (*ca.*) 80° for another 4 hours. After cooling, the solution was filtered to remove the Raney-nickel, which was washed well with water (*ca.* 75 c.c.). The combined filtrate and washings were poured cautiously into H_2SO_4 (C.P., 60 c.c. and water 120 c.c., mixed before use). The hot mixture was left aside for 4 hours, saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ether (35 c.c. $\times$ 6), washed with brine (35 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was distilled off and the residue fractionated to furnish the lactone as a colorless liquid, b.p. 91°/2 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4535, yield 4.8 g. (75%).

(ii) *By Sodium Borohydride Reduction.*—The keto-acid (3.6 g., 0.025 M), dissolved in water (20 c.c.) containing sodium bicarbonate (2.5 g., 0.03 M), was cooled in an ice-bath and sodium borohydride (0.47 g., 0.0125 M) added in one lot with swirling.

After shaking at the ice-temperature for 5 minutes, it was left aside at room temperature (25°) for 4 hours. The mixture was carefully acidified with HCl (conc.) to p_H 2 and left aside overnight (15 hrs.). The almost clear solution was saturated with NaCl, when an oil separated, which was taken up in ether (10 c.c. $\times$ 6) and worked up as above to yield the lactone, b.p. 91°/2 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4535, yield 3.1 g. (97%).

A refractionated (central cut) sample had b.p. 85°/1.5 mm, $\eta_D^{25.5}$ 1.4520, $d_4^{25.5}$ 1.013, M_b 34.10 (calc. 33.99). (Found: C, 65.3; H, 9.1. $C_7H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 65.6; H, 9.4%).

2:3-Dimethyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1-one(I).—To PPA (from P_2O_5 , 7 g. and 85% syrupy phosphoric acid, 3 c.c. Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 262), contained in a test-tube (6" $\times$ 1") and maintained at 97° (immersed in a boiling water-bath), the above lactone (0.64 g., 0.005M) was added in one lot, mixed well with a glass rod and the resulting pale coloured mixture heated at 97° for 4½ hours under dry conditions. The mixture was well mixed thrice during this period of heating by tilting the test-tube so that its contents covered the walls and then flowed back. The red-brown product, obtained at the end of the above heating period, was diluted, with cooling, with ice-water to (ca.) 40 c.c. and to this ammonium sulphate (20 g.) was added and the whole extracted continuously with petroleum ether for 30 hours. From the extract the solvent was fractionated off and the residue distilled to furnish the ketone as a colorless liquid, b.p. 91-92°/22 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4848, yield 0.44 g. (80%).

With larger quantities, the reaction was best carried out in a 3-necked flask with a Hershberg stirrer; the reaction mixture was stirred vigorously for two minutes to effect mixing and then the reaction continued without stirring.

An analytical sample had b.p. 80°/10 mm, $\eta_D^{25.5}$ 1.4855, $d_4^{25.5}$ 0.9677, M_b 32.61 (calc. for $C_7H_{10}O$ $\bar{I}$, 31.88; $E\Sigma_D$ 0.66); λ_{max} 234 m μ (ϵ , 13660). (Frank *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, report b.p. 90-92°/25 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4830, λ_{max} 235 m μ , $\log \epsilon$ 3.04).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) (crude m.p. 214-15°) was obtained as minute red prisms from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 226-27° (decomp.). (Found: N, 19.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4N_4$ requires N, 19.3%).

Bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^7 -octen 1-one (II)

Ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2- β -propionate (Va): (i) By Michael Addition.—Ethyl acrylate (16.65 g., 0.15 M) was allowed to react with ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (19.5 g., 0.125 M) in the presence of potassium *tert.*-butoxide (from potassium 0.1 g.) exactly as described for (1Va). The reaction was more exothermic and the contents had to be cooled with water at (ca.) 15° (instead of tap water) to maintain the temperature between 25° and 30° and finish the addition of the ethyl acrylate within ½ hour. The reddish orange reaction mixture was worked up as described above to provide (Va) as a colorless oil, b.p. 140-42°/1 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4560, yield 29.3 g. (91.5 %).

When in the above reaction, potassium *tert.*-butoxide was replaced by sodium ethoxide (from sodium 0.1 g., alcohol 20 c.c.) the product obtained (from 0.125 M of the keto-ester) had b.p. 185-88°/3 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4400, yield 27 g. (89.4%) and was identified as ethyl γ -carbethoxysuberate by hydrolysis (2 parts of conc. HCl; refluxed for

6 hours) to the corresponding *tricarboxylic acid*, m.p. 111° (white prisms from ethyl acetate) (Cook and Linstead, *loc. cit.*, report b.p. $186^{\circ}/9$ mm for the ester and m.p. 111° for the acid).

(ii) *By Condensation with Ethyl β -Halopropionate*.—Ethyl β -bromopropionate (199 g., 1.1M) and the sodio derivative of ethyl cyclopentanone carboxylate (from sodium 23 g., 1 g. atom and keto-ester 156 g., 1 M) were condensed in toluene (500 c.c.), exactly as described by Sukh Dev (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 817); b.p. $140^{\circ}/1$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4570, yield 210 g. (82%) (Cook and Linstead, *loc. cit.*, report b.p. $189^{\circ}/18$ mm, $\eta_D^{18.4}$ 1.4563, yield 75% from ethyl β -chloropropionate).

When in this reaction ethyl β -chloropropionate replaced the bromo-ester, the yield was almost the same.

cyclopentanone-2- β -propionic Acid (Vb).—The above condensation product (29 g.) was hydrolysed with a mixture of HCl (C.P., 58 c.c.) and water (29 c.c.), as detailed for (IVb) to afford the keto-acid: b.p. $143.44^{\circ}/0.6$ mm; the distillate slowly solidified, m.p. $35-38^{\circ}$, yield 15.8 g. (90%) (Cook and Linstead, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 37°).

$\gamma\delta$ -*cyclopentano- δ -valerolactone (V III)*: (i) *By the Raney-nickel alloy-alkali Method*.—A solution of the keto-acid (24.96 g., 0.16 M) in aqueous NaOH (75 g. in 450 c.c. of water) was reduced with the alloy (37 g.) by following closely the procedure described for the preparation of (VII). On fractionation the lactone was obtained as a colorless liquid, b.p. $107-109^{\circ}/1.5$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4835, yield 12 g. (53.6%).

In one experiment with half the quantities of the materials, the ethereal extract was extracted with saturated aqueous NaHCO_3 to obtain the acidic and neutral portions. The neutral portion on working up afforded the lactone (b.p. $100-101^{\circ}/1$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4835, yield 3.5 g.) leaving practically no distillation residue. A similar distillation of the acidic part yielded the same lactone (2.5 g., same physical constants) and a polymeric residue (*ca.* 4 g.) remained.

A refractionated (central cut) sample had b.p. $109^{\circ}/1.5$ mm, $\eta_D^{25.5}$ 1.4825, $d_4^{25.5}$ 1.101, M_D 36.28 (calc. 36.41). (Found: C, 68.9; H, 8.6. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 68.6; H, 8.6 %).

(ii) *By Sodium Borohydride Method*.—The keto-acid (3.9 g., 0.025 M) was reduced by following the procedure detailed for the lactone (VII). In this case, removal of the solvent from the ether extract gave a viscous product, which was distilled to collect the material boiling up to $130^{\circ}/1$ mm (yield 2.7 g.); a polymeric residue was left. Refractionation of the crude distillate afforded the required lactone, b.p. $122^{\circ}/2.5$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4820, yield 1.6 g. (45.7%).

Bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^7 -octen-1-one (II).—The above lactone (0.7 g., 0.005 M) was treated with PPA in the manner described above for the ketone (I), except that the reaction was conducted at $60^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$ for $4\frac{1}{2}$ hours. On working up the reddish brown reaction mixture in the same manner, the bicyclo-ketone (II) was obtained as a colorless mobile liquid, b.p. $114-15^{\circ}/13$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.5155, yield 0.58 g. (91.8 %).

A refractionated sample had b.p. $110^{\circ}/10$ mm, m.p. $8-10^{\circ}$, $\eta_D^{25.5}$ 1.5190, $d_4^{25.5}$ 1.053, M_D 35.16 (calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$ $\overline{1}$ 34.30; $E \Sigma_D$ 0.70); λ_{max} 240 m μ (ϵ , 11880); *semicarbazone* (by pyridine method) was obtained in white minute silky needles (dilute pyridine),

m.p. 231-32° (decomp.) (Cope and Schmitz, *loc. cit.*, report b.p. 62°/0.9 mm, η_D^{25} 1.5202, d_4^{25} 1.0534, m.p. 17.2-19°; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{cyclohexano}}$ 234m μ , ϵ 11280; semicarbazone m.p. 230-32°).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) (crude m.p. 220-22°) was crystallised first from acetic acid and then from xylene to furnish dark red flat needles, m.p. 221-22°. (Found: N, 18.3. C₁₄H₁₄O₄N₄ requires N, 18.3%).

Bicyclo-[0:3:4]- Δ^8 -nonen-1-one (III)

Ethyl cycloHexanone-2-carboxylate-2- β -propionate (VIa).—The addition of ethyl acrylate (16.65 g., 0.15 M) to ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (21.25 g., 0.125 M) was carried out in the manner described for the analogue (IVa). The reaction was less exothermic as compared to the corresponding case of ethyl cyclopentanone carboxylate. On working up the deep orange-red reaction mixture, the required product (VIa) was obtained as a colorless oil, b.p. 148-49°/0.9 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4630, yield 91.2% (Haworth and Mavin, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 199-202°/15 mm).

When the above reaction was conducted in the presence of sodium ethoxide instead of potassium *tert.*-butoxide, no ring-fission occurred, in contrast to the behaviour of the 5-membered analogue.

cycloHexanone-2- β -propionic Acid (VIb).—The above ester (30 g.), HCl (C.P., 60 c.c.) and water (30 c.c.) were refluxed for 24 hours and then freed of the aqueous HCl etc. under suction from a steam-bath. The cold residue was taken up in aqueous NaOH (6 g. in 60 c.c. of water), washed once with ether (50 c.c.) and the alkaline solution acidified (pH 2), with cooling, with syrupy phosphoric acid. The acid was taken up in ether (50 c.c. $\times$ 3), washed with brine (50 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was flashed off and the residue fractionated, b.p. 153°/0.5 mm; it solidified as it distilled, m.p. 58-62°, yield 16 g. (84.6%); this was used as such for the next step (Haworth and Mavin, *loc. cit.*, report b.p. 155-60°/0.2 mm, m.p. 65-66°).

When the procedure described for (IVb) was followed instead of the above, the yield of the distilled acid fell (75.79%) due to the formation of a lower boiling liquid (b.p. 110-15°/0.6 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4650); this immediately decolorised Br₂ in CCl₄ and may be the enol-lactone (?).

$\gamma\delta$ -cycloHexano- δ -valerolactone (IX): (i) *By the Raney-nickel alloy-alkali Method.*—The keto-acid (23.8 g., 0.14 M) in aqueous NaOH (75 g. in 450 c.c. of water) was reduced with the alloy (37 g.) as described for the lactone (VII): b.p. 115-18°/2 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4790, yield 15.8 g. (70%).

An analytical sample had b.p. 110-12°/1.5 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4815, $d_4^{25.5}$ 1.072, M_D 40.93 (calc. 41.03) (Frank and Bierle, *loc. cit.*, report b.p. 110°/1 mm, η_D^{20} 1.4912).

(ii) *By Sodium Borohydride Method.*—The keto-acid (4.25 g., 0.025 M) was reduced and lactonised by following the procedure described for the preparation of (VII): b.p. 142°/5 mm, yield 3.46 g. (90%).

4:5:6:7-Tetrahydroindan-1-one (III).—The above lactone (0.77 g., 0.005 M) was treated with PPA at 80° $\pm$ 2° by following the procedure detailed for the ketone (I). The data recorded in Table I was obtained by carrying out this reaction for different periods of time. The ketone content of the distillate was measured as follows:

To a weighed sample (ca. 0.15 g.) of the distillate, contained in a conical flask, 40 c.c. of the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent (prepared by dissolving 4 g. of the solid reagent in 40 c.c. of C.P. H_2SO_4 and 60 c.c. of water and diluting to 400 c.c. with 95% ethanol and filtering) was added. The mixture was heated to boiling and boiled for 1 minute and then left aside as such at room temperature for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. After chilling to -5° for 10 minutes, the precipitated derivative was collected on a tared sintered glass funnel under suction. The precipitate was washed with dilute alcohol (1:1; 50 c.c.) and dried at 75° for 15 hours. A check with a pure specimen (*vide infra*) of (III) gave the ketone content of 99.36%.

The samples of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, obtained in the above estimations, were combined (m.p. $218-20^\circ$) and recrystallised twice from xylene to provide dark red leaflets, m.p. $229-30^\circ$, unaltered on admixture with an authentic specimen.

It was not possible to separate completely the ketone (III) from the lactone (IX) by fractionation. The following method was adopted to effect the separation: The distillate (4.0 g., ketone content 65%), dissolved in *n*-hexane (30 c.c.), was stirred vigorously for 2 hours at room temperature with aqueous KOH (1 g. in 40 c.c. of water). The hexane layer was separated and the dark red aqueous phase extracted with hexane (15 c.c. $\times$ 2). After washing the extracts with brine (15 c.c. $\times$ 2) and drying (Na_2SO_4) the solvent was removed (column) and the residue fractionated: b.p. $127-28^\circ/13$ mm, $\eta_D^{20.5}$ 1.5225, yield 2.4 g. (92%). A refractionated sample had b.p. $123^\circ/10$ mm, $\eta_D^{25.5}$ 1.5225, $d_4^{25.5}$ 1.044, M_D 39.76 (calc. for $C_6H_{12}O$ 38.92; $E \Sigma_c$ 0.62); λ_{max} 237 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 13400) (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 264: b.p. $141^\circ/30$ mm, η_D^{20} 1.5225; λ_{max} 237 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.11).

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE-3.

* Received September 20, 1956.